

Air Pollution: A Serious Threat

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1. Air Pollution

The poisonous and harmful substances which contaminate or infect the air are called air pollutants. Air is the mixture of different gases in the environment, polluted by different human activities. Air is very important for the existence of lifecycle on earth. Air is present all around the earth's surface. It is also present in soil and water, due to which living beings can breathe inside the soil and water. Everybody needs air; it is needed for living organisms to remain healthy and safe in the environment.

2. Sources

Many sources pollute the air, in these sources, including natural (forest fire, Volcanic ash, dust particles, etc.) are polluting the air very badly. In human activities, many sources are the origins of air pollution like smoke from vehicles, waste of crops burned, oxides of Sulphur, carbon, and nitrogen. Poisonous gases produced during the decomposition of organic matter and particulate matter like soot, pollens, metallic compounds (compound of lead), Etc., also pollute the air.

2.1. Carbon monoxide

Carbon monoxide is formed by the incineration of coal and fossil fuels, including natural Fuel gas, petrol, oil, Etc. Motor vehicles usually release smoke and industry, which is the main source of carbon monoxide.

2.2. Sulfur dioxide

It is produced by scorching coal or oil in Industrial units. The smoke released by the thermal power station usually contains Sulphur dioxide. Oxides of nitrogen are produced by burning oil and coal at high temperatures in industries, and vehicle engine chlorofluorocarbons are compounds that contain chlorine, fluorine, and carbon atoms. Chlorofluorocarbons are used in aerosol spray, refrigerators, and air conditioning systems. CFCs enter the air on leakage from these appliances and pollute the air. Rotting vegetables and volcanic eruptions are natural sources of air pollution. Fuel-burning in various types of transportation motor vehicles like railway and aircraft is the major source of carbon monoxide 75% in the atmosphere. Sulfur dioxide dissolves in rainwater and causes acid rain. Oxide of nitrogen also causes acid rain. Global warming is unique to the consequences of air pollution. Smog formation in winter is also a cause of air pollution. It forms yellowish-brown haze, which hampers visibility. It also causes many breathing disorders and allergies as it contains poisoning gases.

3. Effects

Air pollution affects human beings as well as plants and aquatic organisms. It causes respiratory diseases in humans like asthma, bronchitis, and emphysema. It can also affect the eyes of many people.

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Carbon monoxide is a poisonous gas; it affects the human organ system and causes headaches, brain damage, and respiratory problems. It reduces the oxygen-carrying capacity in the blood. Carbon Monoxide causes the cardiovascular disorder. Chlorofluorocarbons can cause skin cancer. Oxide of Sulphur can cause pneumonia and lung cancer. Sulfur dioxide can reduce the oxygen concentration in the water and cause the death of marine species, both plants, and animals. It will also cause skin problems in human beings.

Air pollution can cause serious environmental damages to the groundwater, soil, and air. It is also a serious threat to the diversity of life. Studies on the relationship between air pollution and reducing species diversity clearly show the detrimental effects of environmental contaminants on the extinction of animals and plants species. Air deferred toxicants may also cause generative effects in animals. Acid rain, global climate, and temperature inversion changes due to the emissions of greenhouse gasses to the atmosphere are chief environmental influences of air. Lead which is coming from automobile exhaust and industry, causes a serious health problem. It affects the human nervous system and soft the bone of children. Oxides of nitrogen and ozone affect the metabolic function of leaves in plants. These oxides cause damage to leaves like chlorosis, necrosis, obsession and cause acute and chronic injuries in plants. Reduce growth and reproduction.

The upper layer of the atmosphere has ozone which absorbs ultraviolet rays from the sun. Pollutants like chlorofluorocarbons destroy the ozone molecules and break the ozone layer; ozone holes are created, permitting ultraviolet rays to reach the earth's surface. The UV rays increase the temperature and cause skin cancer.

4. How to reduce air pollution?

Reduce the use of automobile sales, use public transport, Plants more plant, Reduce the use of lead and mercury, use filter chimney, never be dusted, Aware the public, established more and more forest in the country, Limit the use of brick fires and industries, Air pollutants coming from industry should be passed

through the filter so that particulate matter is removed before the gases are released out. The use of solar cookers for the productions of gas in industrial-freebee fuel should be used in automobiles.

5. Impact of Air pollution on Environment

The environment is highly affected by the causes of Air pollution along with human health. The most significant environmental influences are as follows: Acid rain (wet or dry) precipitation containing toxic amounts of nitric and sulfuric acids. They can acidify the water, soil environments, damage trees, and plantations, and even damage buildings and sculptures, constructions, and busts.

Haze (smog) is produced when small particles are circulated in the air and reduce the transparency of the atmosphere. Gas emissions are also caused by the air coming from industrial facilities, power plants, automobiles, and trucks.

Ozone occurs both at ground level and in the upper level (stratosphere) of the earth's atmosphere. Ozone from the stratosphere protects us from the sun's damaging ultraviolet (UV) rays. In comparison, ground-level ozone is harmful to human healthiness and is a pollutant. Unluckily, stratospheric ozone is steadily damaged by ozone-depleting stuff (i.e., chemicals, aerosols, and pesticides). If this defensive stratospheric ozone layer is weak, UV radiation can reach our earth, with destructive effects on human life (skin cancer and skin burn). In some parts of Australia, People are harmed by these UV rays. Ozone penetrates through the stomata in plants, convincing them to close, which slabs CO₂ transfer and brings a reduction in photosynthesis.